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“YOU ARE MY ONE AND ONLY”

You are the only one in my heart,
You are the only found in my mind,
I always remember you,
Even where you go,
I will be with you,
Because I love you.

It is not so very important,
For me, if you are far away,
I am waiting here for you,
Anywhere you go,
I will be with you,
Because I love you.

So please my dear believes me,
Because my love is for you,
And you are my one and only.

So please my dear believes me,
Because my heart is for you,
And you are my one and only.